

F A A M

A I R B O R N E
L A B O R A T O R Y

Calibration by comparison of Buck CR2 optical dew-point hygrometer

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Instrument under test: Buck CR2 211-M

Reference instrument: MBW 973-L S/N 18-0719

Reference instrument calibration:

NPL Certificate Ref 2021050317. Quartic calibration applied, coefficients [1.62470E-02, 9.99990E-01, -8.67650E-06, -1.75730E-06, -3.59670E-08]

Calibration procedure:

A Michell Instruments DG2 is used to generate a flow of air of a fixed dewpoint, which is delivered to the hygrometers via stainless steel ¼ inch internal diameter tubing. The flow is split between the MBW 973-L reference instrument and the instrument under test. The flow rate through each instrument is between 0.5 and 1 litres per minute, as measured by the MBW 973-L itself and by a rotameter on the exhaust of the Buck CR2. The test hygrometer mirror is cleaned beforehand. For each calibration point, which are no more than 20 °C intervals between -50 and +20 °C, the instruments are allowed to stabilise before readings of mirror temperature are recorded over no less than 10 minutes for mirror temperatures below -25 °C, and no less than 5 minutes at temperatures above -25 °C. These readings are logged over RS232 for each instrument, and a mean and standard deviation calculated for each calibration point. Should the calibration show a lack of agreement within uncertainty between the MBW 973-L and the Buck CR2, a calibration curve is generated and applied to the Buck CR2 output in processing.

Results:

MBW 973-L 18-0719	Buck CR2 211-M	CR2 Standard deviation
-48.60	-48.08	0.12
-38.40	-38.32	0.08
-28.80	-28.94	0.07
-15.76	-15.99	0.05
-6.09	-6.35	0.05
4.39	4.10	0.02
19.64	19.35	0.02

Quartic calibration coefficients to be applied to Buck CR2 output in processing:
[2.78839E-01, 1.00242E+00, 3.70698E-06, -1.17634E-06, -1.52257E-07]